

Maturation & Individual Difference, “Growth & Development”

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Introduction: The growth of a human being means quantitative increase in his body and it starts from the birth of the child and continues till adolescence and pre-puberty. Its specialty is that its quantitative symptoms are visible. The growth in the physical form of a human being depends on his age, while the development of the human being from body to mind takes place both in quantitative and qualitative ways. This development in humans continues throughout the life. In fact, growth generally refers to structural changes and development refers to functional changes. The difference in the growth and development of a person in the world is a nature and a natural gift of human nature. In the world, a person is not the same as before and they are different from each other on some basis and has acquired some difference. Not only this, even the two children of the same parents are different from each other even though they are determined by the chromosomes of one parent, and due to these differences, they are also considered the future of the next generation and the sense of difference in their physical, mental, moral, intellectual, creativity and emotional point of view is clearly visible. All these characteristics are called individual differences in the language of psychology.

Individual Differences: When we talk about a person or ourselves, we definitely think about various aspects of the person's growth and development. While thinking, the mind definitely sees that how much older is the person in front of me, how fair is he, how smart he is, various kinds of questions come and the questions show the difference in us. This difference is called individual difference in the language of psychology, the study of which is the main objective of this chapter. While studying, two important things definitely come to the mind of the author - such as,

1. There are some elements of similarity in all of us, which follow the developmental pattern in the same way in all of us.

2. Here it has also been seen that every person is oriented and moves towards diversity, due to which the main traits of physical structure, mental abilities, emotional, moral, and cognitive and personality start appearing directly in us.

Here, studying these points indicates that there are some elements which provide similarity in human form, whereas individuals like us are connected on the basis of different quantities of these characteristics or variables, these maintain a characteristic of difference, and all these differences are also considered to be the quantitative measure of individual differences. Commenting on the friendship of this quantitative difference of personality, psychologist Professor Scheinfeld has rightly said in his words, that "In the entire history of the world, there has never been anyone like you and in the infinite infinity of the times to come, there will never be anyone like you." Difference is the natural quality of nature. Complete similarity is not found in any two things of nature. This inequality is the display of individual differences.

Individual differences/variations: Since ancient times, human beings were differentiated among themselves. The history of differentiation of individuals in the history of human beings is also ancient. Even at that time, people were classified on the basis of their physical abilities and capabilities. They were given the status of Brahmin, Kshatriya, Vaishya and Shudra on the basis of their mental strength and mental ability.

On that basis, there was a sense of difference between them. But at that time, no standard measurement was made on the basis of which they could be classified. Whatever classification was there in Indian psychology, it was based only on conjecture and practical projection. Whatever methods were prescribed, they used to be unauthentic. Then gradually modern psychology started expanding and awareness started growing among people. Gradually, psychological tests started being made and meaningful estimates also started coming from those tests.

In the same sequence, in the year 1796, a psychology officer of Greenwich Astronomical Laboratory was dismissed from his job because the accuracy of his work was different from the work of other employees, that is, his observation was different from the observation of other colleagues. After that, this sequence of research was not going to stop. Again in 1816, an astronomer also tried to prove for the first time that the quality of individual difference is found in observation in people. This research of his provided a new basis for individual differences and in the same sequence, Sir Francis Galton wrote his book 'Hereditary Genius' in 1869, in which he discussed individual difference or diversity in a scientific

manner. Since then, people's attention started getting attracted towards individual differences. Then in the twentieth century, modern psychologists like Pearson, Cattell, Terman did their own studies on individual differences and expressed their views.

The result of which was that studies have always been done on this. Since ancient times, human beings were differentiated. The history of differentiation of individuals in the history of human beings is also ancient. Even at that time, people were classified on the basis of their physical abilities and capabilities. They used to get the status of Brahmin, Kshatriya, Vaishya and Shudra on the basis of their mental strength and mental ability. On that basis, there was a sense of difference between them. But at that time, no standard measurement was made on the basis of which they could be classified. Whatever classification was there in Indian psychology, it used to be based only on conjecture and practical projection. Whatever methods were prescribed, they used to be unauthentic. Then gradually modern psychology started expanding and awareness started growing among people. Gradually psychological tests started being made and meaningful estimates also started coming from those tests.

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Meaning of Individual Difference: Individual difference means that on the basis of the physical structure, physical appearance, intelligence, interest in a particular field, their nature, personality and emotional qualities of adolescents, it is seen that among adolescents, one person is found to be different from the other. This difference gives an important place to the difference in the child. Individual differences have a very important place and role in the development of the child. There is no doubt that on the basis of the intelligence, interest, ability and discretion of children, they can get the opportunity of

development at the best level. If individual differences are studied from a holistic point of view, then we can clearly say that the form of difference determined by nature is a very important determining factor for human life. When we read all the things holistically, then it becomes absolutely clear on thinking that this concept of individual difference in human development is a quantitative characteristic and not a qualitative characteristic. Therefore, we can officially declare that the differences found in humans are authentically real. The field of psychology in which the quantitative difference or distinction in human development is studied is called the psychology of individual differences. Many studies in the field of individual differences have refuted such popular views and have made it clear that there are types of differences in the human species determined by certain and natural methods in which these differences are clearly visible, and they can also be classified easily. There is still a wrong concept in our society that if a person is not of mechanical intelligence, then he will not be of natural intelligence either. Then he will be intelligent. On this basis, according to psychology, this two-sided classification is a meaningless and erroneous belief. This quality of human can be defined anywhere that human diversity is a quality of human.

Definition of Individual Differences: Individual difference means when one person appears different from the other person on the basis of complexion, physical structure, intelligence, special abilities, interests, achievements, their nature, their personality traits, then we can say that no two persons are found to be similar in physical structure, intelligence, interest, nature and personality traits etc. That is, on the basis of the things in which differences are found in individuals, there can be mainly three types of differences in individual differences: physical differences, mental differences and personality related differences. After studying various types of differences in the human species, psychologists in the field of modern psychology have tried to define individual differences in their own way, which is being mentioned below.

Skinner has defined individual differences in his words in such a way that “every aspect of personality to be measured is a part of individual difference.” Tyler has tried to define individual differences in his words as follows, “The existence of differences measured in the size and shape of the body, physical functions, movement capabilities, intelligence, achievement, knowledge, interests, attitudes and personality traits has been proven.”

In the same sequence, James Driver also says that “the difference or distinction in the form of a group member in terms of mental and physical characteristics from the average group is called individual difference.”

After studying the above definitions, on the basis of all the facts, it can be clearly said that individual differences are automatically manifested in the physical, emotional, mental and functional characteristics of any child. Under these, the area of individual differences is as wide and vast as the number of people living in this world.

Forms of individual differences: While studying individual differences earlier, it clearly comes out on deep thinking that there are two forms of individual differences.

A. Intra-individual differences: When a person studies the growth and development happening in his life and self-studies his physical, mental, emotional, functional and behavioral dimensions, then he finds that many differences have occurred in these dimensions. The differences thus obtained are called intra-individual differences. All of you know that first you were born as an infant, then you entered childhood, then adolescence and then youth. This stage also transforms you into two types of differences, male and female. At the same time, it is also seen that emotionally you do not remain in one state at all, that is, you do not remain settled. Sometimes you are happy, sometimes you are unhappy, sometimes you are neutral and sometimes you are biased. Sometimes you are in a mood of anger, sometimes you are happy and sometimes you are filled with hatred. This difference is reflected in you as interpersonal difference. If we think further in this sequence, then it becomes clear that our interests, attitudes, motivation and life values, which are always changing, never remain in a neutral state. If we look at the educational life, then in the educational field also sometimes we find ourselves in high achievement, sometimes in average achievement and sometimes in a state of numbness.

B. Interpersonal difference: Under this individual difference, when a person of the society compares himself with another person in his family, society in his physical, emotional, mental and functional aspects, then the difference prevailing on the basis of this area of comparison is called interpersonal difference. We often compare ourselves with the person in front of us on the basis of his colour, appearance, height, physique, mental abilities, emotional animals and their functional skills and achievements and see and understand how much and what kind of differentiating quality is visible in them and us. Due to which we also have the feeling of

improving the life of our fellow beings. Generally, a human keeps thinking that how strong, how rich, how capable, how learned, how valuable, how intelligent, how creative, how prudent he is in comparison to others and he also measures himself in the field of beauty. This competition also helps a person to achieve a position but only when he compares it with a positive feeling.

So, on the basis of both the forms or qualities, when we did a comparative study on intrapersonal differences and interpersonal differences under the current Indian education system, it was seen that the Indian education system gives more emphasis on interpersonal differences as compared to intrapersonal differences. Because through this personal comparison, the education system can easily test, evaluate and prove all the educational achievements of the students. As a result, this type of education system presents extreme competition. Due to which the possibility of educational development in the students increases. This educational development builds their future. Therefore, the comparison of interpersonal differences in a person under the education system should be studied at all times.

Types of individual differences: The differences found on the basis of studies, thoughts and comparative patterns on human growth and development can be divided into three main types of individual differences on the basis of differences.

- 1. Physical differences:** This is the difference for which we study the development of a child, so during development we observe their physical characteristics such as complexion, body structure, height, weight and gender differences, then we find that some people are physically tall, some people are physically short, some people are of average height. Some people are tall, some people are fat, some people are thin, some people are fair, some people are dark, some people are ugly, some people are beautiful, some people are smart, some people are very clumsy. So on the basis of this type of study, we can say that there are physical differences in a child as well. Hence, under physical differences, different people differ in colour, body structure, height, weight, gender, etc.
- 2. Mental differences:** Under mental differences, different people differ in mental qualities as well. Differences are found in mental qualities like intelligence, interest, memory power among people. On the basis of these differences, they are placed in the category of people with mental differences. For example, some people are talented, while some people belong to the stupid and illiterate category. Some people are good at reading, while some people are complete fools in reading. Some people do not understand anything no matter how much you teach them, and

some children understand immediately once someone's life is explained to them, while some children have average level of understanding. Some children remember the things they hear for a long time, while some children remember them for a short time. Some children forget the things they hear very soon.

- 3. Personality Differences:** Under personality differences, the personality of different individuals is of different types. Under this, some individuals are endowed with introvert qualities, while some individuals are endowed with extrovert qualities. Individuals related to these types of differences are of humble nature, sometimes some are of aggressive nature, not only this, some people appear cheerful, happy, while on the other hand some people appear harsh and harsh.

Areas of Individual Differences: Individual differences arise in a person as a result of the interaction of nature and man in the unique and green environment of the individual, following nature. The wide area of individual differences created as a result of the mutual reactions of different heredity, infinite environmental factors also assumes an infinite form in itself. As a result of this infinite compatibility and to understand it broadly, we can divide individual differences into three headings, the details of which are attached herewith.

- a) **Individual differences in cognitive area:** Individual differences in cognitive area have also been classified into 4 parts-)a) Intelligence,)b) Aptitudes,)c) Creativity,)d) Educational achievement
- b) **Individual Differences in emotional area:** Individual differences in emotional area have also been classified into 8 parts.)a) Interest,)b)Attitude,)c) Life values,)d) Motivation,)e) Self-esteem,)f) Emotional stability,)g) Temperament,)h) Personality traits
- c) **Individual Differences Friendships(in psychomotor area:** There are 3 main sub-areas of individual differences in psychomotor area-)a) Physical,)b) Physical endurance,)c) Psychomotor skills

Reasons for individual differences: There is definitely some reason for the differences in the people present in our society, this reason may be created by nature or influenced by humans. Here we will study such reasons which explain individual differences.

.1Genetics: In our society, the biggest reason for individual differences of boys and girls is genetics. This genetics is received by children from their parents. Psychology says that the chromosomes received from parents determine their development, and this development

awakens individual differences in them. In the field of psychology, psychologists like Dalton Person Terminus have proved in their research studies that the inheritance of boys and girls is responsible to a great extent for many physical, mental and personality related traits. What qualities a child will get from his parents in inheritance depends only on the cooperation of his parents. Due to the number of chromosomes received during the cooperation of parents being different, differences are found in the children of the same parents.

.2Environment: The environment around the child also affects individual differences. Actually, there are many types of environment like geographical environment, social environment and cultural environment. The kind of environment in which a person like you lives, his physical development, mental development, emotional development, character development takes place accordingly. Like Pasighat is a cold and dry environment where there are mountains, forests, gardens all around, so the children here are also born in the same form. Their development takes place accordingly. The language style, lifestyle, food habits, nature of uneducated families, nature of educated families develop the children in the same form. Due to the difference in the environment in these people, physical differences, mental differences and emotional differences are seen in them.

.3Maturity: Maturity means becoming mature. Maturity is related to the age of the person. Children of different ages attain maturity physically and mentally in different ways. And this maturity also brings individual differences in those children.

.4Intelligence: Intelligence is also a major reason for individual differences in a child. Because the intelligence of two children in a group is not the same. Some are good at studies and some are weak. Individual differences arise on the basis of intelligence.

.5Gender Difference: Gender difference is a big reason for individual differences. Gender differences prevalent in the society, dividing people into male and female class is also an example of gender differences.

.6Health: It is said that the development will be as per the health. Hence, there is a lot of difference in the developmental aspects of a good healthy person and an unhealthy person. This difference causes individual differences in them.

.7Family status: Family status is also a big reason for individual differences. The intellectual, social, moral, physical development of a child of high socio-economic status is very different from the development of children of low socio-economic status and the development of a child of medium socio-economic status. This difference causes individual differences in them.

.8Caste and race: In society, caste and race also have an effect on the development of the child. A person belonging to a higher social caste thinks differently from a child belonging to a lower caste and race. This thought creates individual differences in them, which makes this difference stronger. In this way, a child belonging to a lower caste considers himself weaker than a child belonging to a higher caste, due to which his social, moral and mental development is affected. Due to a gap like discrimination between them, their developmental aspect also becomes different. This difference is an example of individual difference. It is often seen that a child belonging to a higher caste like Kshatriya Brahmin is courageous and knowledgeable, whereas a child belonging to a Vaishya or Shudra is strong in business and service. This dominance of their respective fields also becomes an example of the difference between them from an educational point of view.

Characteristics of Individual Differences:

- 1. Variance:** When we measure a particular group on the basis of some physical and mental qualities, then we come to know that the spread of those qualities is present in the group and is found in different amounts in different members and this measurement is important for the teacher. The teacher should always study it.
- 2. Equality:** When a researcher measures the quality or expertise of a particular group, then the distribution obtained is for equality on the letter. That is, we can say that the curve of the distribution is bell-shaped. That is, the study of happiness can be a good opportunity for the teacher to improve his teaching work. Therefore, the teacher should teach the general to other teachers.
- 3. Speed Variation:** Speed variation is a very big example of bringing individual differences in human society because due to this quality, there are differences in the context of the child from person to person, just as the speed of development of different traits is different in a person himself.
- 4. Mutual relationship:** Under individual differences, the characteristics of a person are inter-related and the evidence of this is that if a child is physically healthy, then he will definitely be mentally healthy as well and when he is mentally healthy, he can acquire educational qualifications properly. That is, for an achievement, mental development in a child is necessary and for mental development, physical health of the child is also necessary. Hence, the characteristics acquired individually in a person are inter-related. That is, change in one characteristic affects the other characteristic.

Keeping in mind the characteristics of individual differences, the teacher in the field of education wants to provide such opportunities to his students in the interest of which their proper and maximum development can take place, because modern psychology says that the centre of education is the child, and the key to the development of the child is his individual difference and a deep understanding of this individual difference. Hence, child-Centered education will have to nurture and encourage individual differences to get positive and desired results on truly fertile ground.

Roll of Schools for Students: In this context, in order to nurture the individual differences of the child, the teacher follows some important statements in the school system: –

- i. It is the duty of the teacher to identify the ability of each student and determine his level according to his ability.
- ii. It is also the duty of the teacher to identify those students with special abilities and aptitude from among the students present in the class and also identify their level of speciality on the basis of those special abilities.
- iii. It is the duty of the teacher to identify those students who are suffering from disability and also determine their level on the basis of their individual differences.
- iv. A teacher should identify those children who are deprived of facilities.
- v. It is essential for a teacher to bring diversity in the curriculum in the class keeping in mind the individual differences.
- vi. It is the responsibility of the teacher to make provision of different types of programs and institutions for the students so that their development can take place in the right manner.
- vii. A teacher should always arrange for individual instruction because this instruction develops the child's abilities to the maximum and the process of teacher and education also runs smoothly.
- viii. A school should also make arrangements for capable teachers keeping in mind individual differences and should also arrange for proper facilities and equipment so that proper education can be provided to students affected by individual differences.

Maturation:

Conclusion: Individual differences have become such a subject in today's time that from Indian psychology to western psychology, everyone has presented their views on this, where Indian psychology has a view.

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